

IMPACTS OF DIFFERENCES IN POLITICAL IDEOLOGIES ON STUDENTS' SOCIAL RELATIONSHIPS

Eunice Nicolle R. Guyod, Nikko C. Balao, Jessa Marie L. Alvarez

BA Political Science
Isabela State University-Cauayan

ABSTRACT

Political ideologies have a significant impact on an individual's social relationships especially during political discussions, wherein it can manifest either positive or negative consequences. Previous research has revealed that individuals may refrain from engaging in political discussions if they perceive political differences with their family or friends, as tight-knit relationships often result in similar political affiliations, at the same time teachers and employees can shape young people's societal involvement by bringing their ideologies within institutions. Furthermore, when political discussions turn into a fixed pattern of disagreement, there is a tendency for individuals to withdraw from the conversation. With these occurrences, the researchers interviewed 10 students and used a semi-structured interview guide aimed at exploring how differences in political ideologies affect students' social relationships, particularly with their family, peers, and teachers or mentors. The findings revealed that students view differences in political ideologies as an avenue for national progress, emphasizing the importance of respect and acknowledgment in conversing with individuals holding different political ideologies. However, four out of 10 respondents avoid political discussions within the family due to differing political ideologies, prioritizing family relationships over ideological debates, while a similar proportion choose to compromise pride to maintain friendships despite the pain it caused them. Moreover, students tend to listen to and respect teachers' political ideologies, as they are more knowledgeable and are considered supreme over them.

Keywords: *political ideologies, social relationships, students' social relationships*

INTRODUCTION

The South-South Cooperation (SSC) as defined by the United Nations, is a technical cooperation among developing countries in the Global South. This serves as a tool for states, international organizations, civil society, and the private sector to collaborate and share knowledge skills, and successful initiatives in specific areas such as agricultural development, human rights, urbanization, health, climate change, etc., (United Nations, 2019). Its significant contribution to development such as enhancing the capacities of institutions for better cooperation makes it essential in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals particularly, Goal 16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions.

In strengthening institutions, political participation is crucial wherein individuals can share their political ideologies during political discussion. These ideologies influence the way humans view the world. Harrison and Boyd (2018) described ideologies as an intellectual 'map' that helps us navigate the world, understand our place in it, and analyze the political and social events that occur around us. The accuracy and worth of these maps vary, and can only be evaluated by comparing them to facts and debating with others. In politics, ideology is defined as an individual's political beliefs, attitudes, values, and affiliations, shaping views on how a political institution or government should function (Bernardo, 2017). Consequently, these ideologies affect individuals' everyday choices

and interactions within their social circles thereby, influencing their social relationships (Rawat & Gahlot, 2021; Fieldhouse & Cutts, 2021).

Political ideology is influenced by various social factors, including family, peers, education, gender, and occupation (Turan & Tiras, 2017). The family, in particular, is the most important institution in which all social and political processes are inherited, as it provides the first social context for a child (Van Ditmars, 2017). Peers and friendships also contribute significantly, because groups tend to behave similarly thus, frequently vote for the same political party. Furthermore, individuals are more likely to approach and make friends with others if they share similar political characteristics (Campos et al., 2017; Huber & Malhotra, 2017). Teachers as well, play a role in creating a room for sociopolitical discussion. Students develop their attitudes toward societal participation through schools, and the teacher's initiative creates an open climate in which students are willing and able to interact and discuss societal issues. (Wanders et al., 2019).

With these occurrences, the researchers sought to find out how differences in political ideologies affect students' social relationships, particularly among their family, peers, and teachers or mentors. Specifically, this study is conducted to answer the following questions: (1) How do students view differences in Political Ideology? (2) How do students interact with people with different political ideologies compared to them? And (3) How do political differences in ideologies affect their relationships with (Family, Peers, Teachers/Mentor)

METHODS

This study employed a qualitative research approach to understand people's beliefs, experiences, attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. (Pathak et al., 2013). The researchers gathered the needed data through a one-on-one interview, using a semi-structured interview guide validated by experts in the field. The interview guide has three parts. Part I includes questions on how students view differences in Political Ideology, Part II comprises questions about how students interact with people with different Political Ideologies compared to them, and Part III contains questions on how Differences in political ideologies affect their relationship with family, peers, and teachers/mentors. These guide questions were answered by ten (10) students from the School of Arts and Sciences Department who were selected through convenience sampling.

The respondents were initially briefed about the purpose of the study and assured that their anonymity and the confidentiality of the interview would be maintained. Subsequently, the researchers provided the respondents with informed consent, which they signed to voluntarily participate in the study. The data gathered was analyzed through thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers sought permission from the Dean of the School of Arts and Sciences Department to conduct the study. Upon securing permission from the Dean, the researchers started to interview the Respondents. Orientation was given to them, wherein the researchers explained the details of the study. Consequently, the respondents were provided with informed consent which was signed voluntarily to participate in the study.

The researchers also asked for the respondents' permission to audio record the interview proceedings, and they consented to it. Furthermore, the researchers ensured that the respondent's identity and responses were kept with utmost anonymity and confidentiality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students Views on Differences in Political Ideology

Harrison and Boyd (2018) claimed that belief holders are not required to have their beliefs "proven" by logical or scientific testing as these beliefs serve as "truth" and "reality" for them. The respondents were asked if they held political ideologies, and all of them did. Then the researchers asked for a brief discussion about their political ideologies, and respondents emphasized their ideal leader and society. They believe that a leader must

be someone who possesses strong leadership and transparency. A government that promotes gender inclusivity and focuses on the goodness of society as a whole.

Subsequently, when respondents were asked about their views on the differences in political ideologies, one respondent stated: “We have our differences, but I think, based on my observation, I see that there are groups of people who strictly follow whatever their leader says, while others have diverse opinions even within the same group. So, I think they have their political ideologies, and we should respect that.” (Respondent 1, personal communication, June 14, 2023.) As stated in the study by Mallinson and Hatemi (2018), individuals often modify their perspective and adjust their stance to secure social approval. On the other hand, Respondent 3 sees differences in political ideologies as a way for everyone to unite for the betterment of the country as reflected in this statement: “The political ideologies I see here in the Philippines are like 'pinakbet'—even though we have disparities and different views, we still unite to improve our country. That's our goal, right? Despite our differing perspectives, we are all aiming for success and the betterment of society.”

However, respondent 5 stated: “I view differences in political ideologies as a way for us to become a progressive nation because we need differences, and it is important to acknowledge different political ideologies because it is our way to analyze the “SWOT” in politics.” This pointed out that differences in political ideologies can serve as an avenue for a nation to be progressive. In contrast, respondent 7 stated: “I viewed differences in political ideologies as a source of conflict. “Yes, it is evident that if people have different political ideologies, there is a tendency for them to fight, which can also cause misunderstandings.”

Students' Interactions With People With Different Political Ideologies Compared To Them

According to Rawat and Gahlot (2020), political ideology plays a significant role in shaping individuals and affects their everyday choices and interactions with others, especially within their social circle. When researchers asked how their interaction with people who have different political ideologies than theirs, respondents stated that respect and acknowledgment are important when interacting with people of different political ideologies than yours. This is clearly expressed by respondents who stated “I think respect is important. Let's respect their view and then we can listen to it. We can also consider it and see how it aligns or clashes with our ideologies.” (Respondent 2, personal communication, June 14) and another one is “It's normal to talk to them because, as a Political Science student, there are manners and characteristics you should possess. Just because you have different political beliefs from others doesn't mean you should cancel them out. You should respect them because, at the end of the day, respect begets respect. If you respect their views, then they will respect you.” (Respondent 1, personal communication, June 14)

These perspectives align with Singh (2016), who argues that respecting other people's political views goes beyond a person's legal rights; it has to do with one's moral character and simply being a decent person. Everyone has the freedom to form opinions based on the information they have, hence, it is acceptable to judge someone depending on which candidate they favor. The golden rule is the most fundamental norm controlling society, however, it is inappropriate to let it influence your behavior and the way you act toward others.

Three of the respondents stated that they find it hard to communicate with someone who has different political ideologies than theirs and tend not to talk with them when they find others too stiff with their ideologies and show narrow-mindedness during political discussions, to avoid argumentation. When asked how their interaction ended up and how their experiences were, respondents stated that argumentation can't be avoided when different ideologies clash; however, argumentation was settled properly to not risk their relationship.

Effects of Differences in Political Ideologies on Students' Relationship

Family

When the respondents were asked about their experience of having different political ideologies among their family members, four out of 10 respondents stated that among the family members, they are the only ones

who have a different political ideology. This is why they avoid conversations with one of their family members about politics. As Respondent 10 stated, "Yeah, I always avoid topics about politics around my family members now." This is reflected in the study of Levinsen & Yndigejn (2015), individuals' participation in political discussions with parents and friends is an important part of the political socialization process. Those who believe their father, mother, or friends have more distant political views are less likely to engage in political discussions with each of them.

When asked about how they handle these differences in political ideologies, some respondents ended up having discourse with their family members however, this was settled properly. One respondent stated, "We don't let political differences slide or allow them to affect our personal lives. When it comes to relationships with family members, that should remain intact." (Respondent 1, personal communication, June 14, 2023). In general, students tend to avoid political topics within their families to avoid conflict and misunderstanding.

Peers

Tucker (2016) claimed that friendship is the way we conceive about trade. In economics, complete similarity does not allow for the exchange of goods and services. They exchange ideas because each respondent thinks the exchange will make them better off than they were beforehand. Exchange only becomes mutually profitable in the midst of mismatched expectations. The same holds for friendship. We require hearing many viewpoints. We require outside perspectives. Even if we don't agree with all they say, we may still try to comprehend other people and the world by listening to what they have to say in a sincere, friendly, and honest manner. In other words, these kinds of friendships benefit us.

Four out of 10 respondents are prepared for the outcomes and lower their pride to save their friendships or peers. One of the respondents stated "A lot of my friends have different political ideologies, and I handle it by treating it as a joke. We don't take it personally because it's far from the core of our relationship." (Respondent 1, personal communication, June 14, 2023), treating political discussions in peers as a source of joke. On the other hand, one respondent stated "The hurt or resentment towards my peers is still there, but we need to accept that, no matter what happens, we are still friends. We have to maintain our togetherness and relationship with them because, at the end of the day, they are the ones we can rely on. So, we need to let go and forget." (Respondent 3, personal communication, June 14) which shows that students have hidden resentment towards their peers however they tend to disregard it to keep their relationship.

Teachers/Mentors

The respondents were asked about their experience of having different political ideologies with their teachers or mentors. Some respondents stated that they never encountered or never had a conversation about political ideologies with one of their teachers. Some stated that when teachers start to tell their political ideologies in class, students tend to listen to them. As reflected in the following responses: "Of course, some of our teachers are quite traditional. I don't know how, but I just respect them. Some people will insist on what they know, and you can't change their minds, so you just respect them and move on." (Respondent 2, personal communication, June 14, 2023) Another one "We need to be a bit hypocritical because they are our teachers, and we need to respect them. We don't have the right to question them because they are professionals, and we are just students." (Respondent 3, personal communication, June 14, 2023) And lastly, "That's something I still struggle with. They are ahead of us, more knowledgeable, and considered superior. But it's a matter of respect, maybe." (Respondent 8, personal communication, Jun 14, 2023) Supporting the study by Swigart et al., (2020) that employees, whether intentionally or unintentionally, bring their political ideologies into organizations. This points out that students somehow avoid political arguments with their teachers to avoid conflict between them.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Differences in political ideologies exist in our society. There are instances that these differences lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, and strained relationships among family, peers, and teachers or mentors. Our study

revealed that the impact of differences in political ideologies varies in every student. They are very much aware of the existence of differences in political ideologies within their social circle. And have emphasized that respect is a fundamental aspect that every individual must possess and practice when interacting with others holding different political ideologies. However, even though respect is practiced, disagreements and arguments cannot be avoided. Many tend to avoid political discussions with family members to maintain harmony in the household. Despite that, some students believe that engaging in political discourse can widen their perspective of different political ideologies. While among peers, students tend to compromise and prioritize friendship over political debates. However, some have mentioned that due to conflicting ideologies, relationships are ruined. In educational settings, on the other hand, students respect their teachers' political ideologies, as they uphold their teacher's superiority and authority over them.

Out of all the data collected, we have concluded that regardless of the differences in political ideologies, respect, and consideration are important as we live in a democratic country in which the people of society have freedom of speech, freedom of expression, and freedom to choose what is best for the society.

REFERENCES

- Algan, Y., Dalvit, N., Do, Q.-A., Le Chapelain, A., & Zenou, Y. (2023). *Friendship networks and political opinions: A natural experiment among future French politicians*. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4593953>
- Amati, V., Meggiolaro, S., Rivellini, G., & Zaccarin, S. (2018). Social relations and life satisfaction: The role of friends. *Genus*, 74(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41118-018-0032-z>
- Arshad, A., & Hassan, S. A. (2014). Role of new media in political discussion and changing voting behavior of university students. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(7), 4-9.
- Badaru, K. A., & Adu, E. O. (2021). The political awareness and participation of university students in post-apartheid South Africa. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 6(3), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2021.22>
- Bernardo, A. B. I. (2017). Exploring political values of Filipinos using an etic approach. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, 50(2), 7-38.
- Bertodatti, & Koyzis. (2021). How does politics shape the way we see the world. *The Ethics and Religious Liberty Commission*. <https://erlc.com/resource-library/articles/>
- Binder, A., Raffael, H., Jörg, M., & Diana, S. (2021). Dealigned but mobilized? Insights from a citizen science study on youth political engagement. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 24(2), 232-249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2020.1714567>
- Campos, C. F. S., Heap, S. H., & de Leon, F. L. L. (2017). The political influence of peer groups: Experimental evidence in the classroom. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 69(4), 963-985. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oeq/gpw065>
- Dimitrova, D. V., & Jörg, M. (2018). Social media in political campaigning around the world: Theoretical and methodological challenges. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 95(2), 333-342.
- Turan, E., & Tıraş, Ö. (2017). Family's impact on individual's political attitude and behaviors. *International Journal of Psycho-Educational Sciences*, 6(2).

- Feldman, S., & Huddy, L. (2014). Not so simple: The multidimensional nature and diverse origins of political ideology. *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 37, 312-313. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X13002562>
- Fieldhouse, E., & Cutts, D. (2021). Do as I say or do as I do? How social relationships shape the impact of descriptive and injunctive norms of voting. *British Journal of Political Science*, 51(4), 1516-1528. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007123420000058>
- Armstrong, G. M. (2015). *Examining the parent-child political relationship* (Master's thesis, Oklahoma State University). https://shareok.org/bitstream/handle/11244/25743/Armstrong_okstate_0664M_13999.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1
- Heiss, R., & Jörg, M. (2021). Funny cats and politics. Do humorous context posts impede or foster the elaboration of news posts on social media? *Communication Research*, 48(1), 100–124. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0093650219826006>
- Huber, G. A., & Malhotra, N. (2017). Political homophily in social relationships: Evidence from online dating behavior. *The Journal of Politics*, 79(1), 269-283.
- Klaus, L., & Carsten, Y. (2015). Political discussions with family and friends: Exploring the impact of political distance. *The Sociological Review*, 63(1), 72-91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-954X.12263>
- Kiehne, E., & Ayón, C. (2016). Friends or foes: The impact of political ideology and immigrant friends on anti-immigrant sentiment. *The Journal of Sociology & Social Welfare*, 43(3), Article 9.
- Labor, J. D. (2017). Filipino college students' views on the value of physical appeal to political leadership. *Southeast Asian Journal of Economics*, 11(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.21002/seam.v11i1.7736>
- Levensen, K., & Yndigegn, C. (2015). Political discussions with family and friends: Exploring the impact of political distance. *The Sociological Review*, 63(1), 72-91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-954X.12263>
- Mallinson, D. J., & Hatemi, P. K. (2018). The effects of information and social conformity on opinion change. *PLoS ONE*, 13(5), e0196600. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196600>
- Miller, J. M., Saunders, K. L., & Farhart, C. E. (2016). Conspiracy endorsement as motivated reasoning: The moderating roles of political knowledge and trust. *American Journal of Political Science*, 60(4), 824-844. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12234>
- Nam, T. (2012). Dual effects of the internet on political activism: Reinforcing and mobilizing. *Government Information Quarterly*, 29(4), 590-597.
- Nordin, A. H. M., & Smith, G. M. (2018). Friendship and the new politics: Beyond community. *Global Discourse*, 8(4), 615-632. <https://doi.org/10.1332/204378918X15453934506029>
- Oc, B., Netchaeva, E., & Kouchaki, M. (2021). It's a man's world! The role of political ideology in the early stages of leader recruitment. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 162, 24–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2020.10.017>
- Ostrowski, M. S. (2021). Ideology studies and comparative political thought. *Journal of Political Ideologies*, 27(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13569317.2021.2020994>

- Pathak, V., Jena, B., & Kalra, S. (2013). Qualitative research. *Perspectives in Clinical Research*, 4(3), 192. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2229-3485.115389>
- Šerek, J., Lacinová, L., & Macek, P. (2012). Does family experience influence political beliefs? Relation between interparental conflict perceptions and political efficacy in late adolescence. *Journal of Adolescence*, 35(3), 577-586.
- Singh, A. (2016). The importance of respecting political differences. *TJToday*. <https://www.tjtoday.org/19035/showcase/the-importance-of-respecting-political-differences/>
- Swigart, K. L., Anantharaman, A., Williamson, J. A., & Grandey, A. A. (2020). Working while liberal/conservative: A review of political ideology in organizations. *Journal of Management*, 46(6), 1063–1091. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206320909419>
- Turan, E., & Tıraş, O. (2017). Family's impact on individual's political attitude and behaviors. *International Journal of Psycho-Educational Sciences*, 6(2).
- Tucker, J. A. (2016). Don't lose friendships over politics. *Foundation for Economic Education*. <https://fee.org/articles/don-t-lose-friendships-over-politics/>
- United Nations. (2019). What is "South-South cooperation" and why does it matter? *UN DESA | United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs*. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/intergovernmental-coordination/south-south-cooperation-2019.html>
- Van Ditmars, M. M. (2017). Family & politics; The enduring influence of the parental home in the development and transmission of political ideology. *European University Institute Department of Political and Social Sciences*.